

Experimental Study and Numerical Simulation of Precast Concrete Frames with Debonded Reinforcement

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Abstract. This paper utilizes experimental and numerical studies to investigate the seismic behavior of precast concrete frames. The system is composed of monolithic columns and composite precast concrete beams with debonded reinforcement at the beam end, with the purpose of distributing plasticity over a larger rebar length to improve the seismic performance of traditional precast concrete frames. In the experimental program, two half scale precast concrete frames, with and without debonded rebar, were tested under quasi-static cyclic lateral load. The observations during the test, load-displacement curves, stiffness, energy dissipating capacity and self-centering capacity are discussed. The experimental findings demonstrate that rebar debonding lead to reduced strain in tensile reinforcement and improved ductility, as well as better self-centering capacity. **The performance of the specimens is evaluated according to ACI 374, which demonstrates that this precast system is applicable to high seismic regions.** In the numerical simulation study, a macro-based finite element (FE) model was developed using fiber-section beam-column element with a modified rebar constitutive model to take into account the effect of rebar buckling which was observed in the test. The results of the FE model fit well with those of the test in terms of global structural behavior and local stress-strain response. In addition, the effects of debond length and effective width of floor slab were analyzed parametrically in the numerical study, which showed that the effective width of floor slab could be taken as 750mm and the strain in the rebar decrease with debond length.

Key word seismic behavior; precast concrete; frame; debond; finite element analysis

Introduction

Precast concrete structures have been extensively used in buildings and bridges because they have the advantages of high efficiency, good quality, labor savings and environmental protection [1-4]. However, locally induced strain in the tensile reinforcement at the interface between precast concrete members is a serious issue in precast concrete structures, which often leads to premature fracture of rebar at the plastic hinge locations under seismic events. A number of solutions were proposed to mitigate such concentrated damage to

the longitudinal reinforcement, such as moving the connection plane away from the face of the column [5-7], using post-tensioned beam-column joints [8, 9], implementing a damping device [10-12] and adopting grouted sleeve connections [13, 14] et. al. Of these solutions, rebar debonding at the plastic hinge region is the most economic one because it is convenient and does not require other changes to the connections details [15, 16]. Because of its advantages, debonding of reinforcement has been widely considered in precast concrete structures, especially in precast beam-column connections [17-20].

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Fig 1 Conceptual diagram of plastic hinge length

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The purpose of debonding is to extend the plastic hinge region at the end of the beam [21], as shown in Fig 1. In a cast-in-place joint the longitudinal rebar will initially yield at the interface and under increased demands will tend to generate inelasticity over a length called the plastic hinge region. As a result of the large strains in the reinforcement bond will be locally degraded resulting in a debonded region which will go through the beam-column joint (Fig 1a). While in precast concrete systems the connection of the precast beam and column results in a weak interface where the majority of deformation tends to occur. The debonded region will have a much smaller length which is limited in a region adjacent to the gap between the precast elements (Fig 1b). Debonding the tensile reinforcement at the beam face will conceptually spread the locally induced deformation caused by the weakened plane over greater rebar length so that early rebar yielding and fracture can be prevented to improve the seismic performance of the frame structure (Fig 1c).

A number of experimental studies were conducted on the structural behavior of concrete members with debonded reinforcement. Kawashima et. al investigated the effect of debonding the longitudinal reinforcement in a 1.45 m tall square concrete column with a cross-sectional width of 400 mm [22]. The tests demonstrated that the strain on a debonded longitudinal bar was much smaller than the strain on a longitudinal bar in the standard column. Similar results were obtained by debonding the longitudinal bars inside a footing. They concluded that the debonding is an effective way to increase the ductility of columns [23]. John et. al used debonding of reinforcing bars to prevent the

formation of undesirable torsion and shear cracks in reinforced concrete interior wide-band beam-column joints. This detailing showed stable performance up to the maximum applied 4% nominal drift [24]. Yu and Tan studied the progressive collapse behavior of RC frames and used debonding of beam bottom reinforcement as a means of improvement. They found that debonding mitigated the strain concentration which resulted in a 67% increase of rotational capacity before the first bar fracture [17]. Nikoukalam and Sideris tested large-scale reinforced concrete columns with partially debonded reinforcement. They concluded that debonding decreased strain localizations in the reinforcement and self-centering improved with debonded length [25].

In the framework of numerical studies, Kurama et. al. developed an analytical model based on fiber beam-column elements to investigate the behavior of unbonded post-tensioned (UPT) precast concrete walls using DRAIN-2DX. UPT steel bars were modeled by truss element. Perez et. al. used Kurama's model to consider five critical limit states in the seismic behavior of UPT walls [26]. They concluded that the fiber model was sufficiently accurate for estimating UPT wall response under earthquake loading. Gavridou et. al. developed a nonlinear model of the 4-story precast concrete building that was tested on the E-Defense shake table. In their model, UPT walls were simulated using a combination of inelastic shear wall elements and truss elements in Perform-3D [27]. Besides these macro-based beam-column element models, three-dimensional (3D) models are also used to simulate debonding. Ou et. al. established a detailed 3D FE model to predict the behavior of precast

129 UPT concrete columns under seismic load [28]175
130 Henry et. al. developed a 3D FE model of precast76
131 self-centering walls explicitly considering the uplift77
132 and changes in post-tensioning stresses. Good78
133 correlation is achieved with the results from the79
134 experimental test for both global and local80
135 responses [29]. 181

136 In spite of these studies on debonding of82
137 longitudinal reinforcement in reinforced concrete83
138 cast-in-place and precast systems, test data on84
139 precast concrete frame structures with debonded85
140 rebar are rare. A macro-based finite element model86
141 considering debonding and buckling of rebars is87
142 still needed to be developed to further understand88
143 the behavior of precast concrete frame with89
144 debonding. The present research focuses on the90
145 experimental and numerical studies to investigate91
146 the seismic behavior of precast concrete frames92
147 with rebar debonding at the plastic hinge region of93
148 the beam. Two half scale precast concrete frames94
149 with and without debonded rebar, are tested under95
150 quasi-static cyclic lateral load. The performance of96
151 the tested frame is evaluated in terms of97
152 load-displacement curves, stiffness, energy98
153 dissipating capacity and self-centering capacity99
154 Then a macro-based finite element (FE) model is100
155 developed using fiber-section beam-column101
156 element with a modified rebar constitutive model102
157 taking into account the effect of rebar buckling. The103
158 effects of debond length and effective width of the104
159 floor slab are analyzed parametrically. 205

160 Test specimens 206

161 The prototype structure is a four-story four-bay in107
162 the longitudinal direction and two-bay in the108
163 transverse direction moment resisting frame as109
164 shown in Fig 2. The frame structure was designed110
165 according to Chinese design code GB50011 [30]111
166 and GB50010 [31], which is similar to ACI 318 [32]112
167 and ASCE 7 [33]. In the frame system, all113
168 beam-column connections are moment connection114
169 so that the lateral load can be evenly distributed to115
170 each parallel moment frame. Each bay is 6 m long116
171 and each story is 3 m high. The cross section of the117
172 exterior and interior column are 600×600 mm and118
173 600×800 mm, respectively. The beam has a cross119
174 section of 300×600 mm. The system utilize120

precast beams and floor slabs. Continuity with the
frame is made with cast-in-place columns and
topping slabs as illustrated in Fig 3.

The test specimens are half-scale two-story two-bay
frames due to experimental space constraints. The
dimension and details of specimens are illustrated
in Fig 3 and Fig 4. Two specimens are tested. The
beam-column connections of the specimen are
shown in Fig 5. Specimen PCF-1 is traditional
cast-in-place column and composite concrete beam
frame. The thickness and width of the floor slab are
70 mm and 1150 mm, respectively. Specimen
PCF-2 has the same configuration and rebar details
with PCF-1 except that the bottom longitudinal
reinforcements of the beam are debonded from the
face of column to a distance of 300 mm inside the
beam. The debonded length is equal to the height of
the beam, which is one half of the hoop
confinement length specified in ACI 318-14 [32].
The debonding is created by PVC tubes with an
inner diameter and thickness of 14.7mm and 1.5mm,
respectively. The inside surface of the PVC tube is
lubricated to eliminate the effect of friction between
the rebar and PVC tube. The PVC tubes span the
debonded length and are sealed with foam sealant at
their ends before concrete placement.

The sequence of construction follows traditional
Chinese erection procedures and is as follows a)
prefabricate the precast beams and slabs, b) set the
reinforcement and formwork of the foundation and
columns, c) Cast concrete for the foundation and
column, d) install precast beam and slab, e) set the
top rebars of the beam and slab, f) cast top concrete
for the beam and slab. The construction of this
system is similar to that of cast-in-place concrete
structures, except that the formwork of the floor
slab is eliminated by using the precast beam and
slab. Compared to the total precast system, this
system has a lower requirement for fabrication and
construction precisions and better integrity because
of the cast-in-situ concrete work. Due to its
advantages, this kind of frame system is
recommended in the Chinese specification for
precast concrete structures [34].

The material properties of the rebar and concrete
are listed in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. The

221 compressive strength of concrete was measured
222 from a concrete cube with a side length of 150 mm

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Fig 2 Prototype structure

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Fig 3 Dimensions of test specimen (all dimensions are in mm)

Fig 4 Details of test specimen (all dimensions are in mm)

Fig 5 Beam-column connection

Table 1 Material property of rebar

Diameter /mm	Yield stress /MPa	Ultimate stress/MPa	Modulus /MPa	Elongation
6	488.0	607.0	2.2×10^5	29%
12	433.0	737.0	2.0×10^5	23%

Table 2 Material property of concrete

Specimen	Location	f_{cu} /MPa
PCF-1	Precast	33.8
	Cast-in-place	37.3
PCF-2	Precast	34.2

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235 **Test setup**

236 The general features of the test setup are illustrated
 237 in Fig 7. The axial compressive load on top of each
 238 column was applied by two prestressed steel rods
 239 placed on either side of the column. Vertical jacks
 240 were installed between the rigid overhead beam and
 241 the column. The steel rod has a diameter of 40 mm
 242 and a nominal tensile strength of 400 MPa. It was
 243 connected with the rigid overhead beam at the top
 244 and a pinned bearing at the bottom so that the
 245 vertical load could move freely with the horizontal
 246 load. Lateral braces were attached to the reaction
 247 frame to avoid out-of-plan deformation of the test
 248 specimen.
 249 The design axial load is equivalent to $0.12f_cA_c$ at the
 250 bottom section of the columns of the first story
 251 where f_c is the specified concrete strength, 23.4
 252 MPa, and A_c is the cross-sectional area of the
 253 column. Therefore, the target vertical loads were
 254 250 kN and 350 kN for the exterior column and
 255 interior column, respectively. The vertical load
 256 remained nearly constant throughout the test. The
 257 cyclic quasi-static horizontal load is applied at the
 258 top of the frame by a 1000 kN MTS actuator. The
 259 horizontal loading program is a displacement
 260 controlled procedure. The loading history is shown
 261 in Fig 6. Three cycles were repeated at each
 262 displacement amplitude.

Fig 6 Loading history

266 **Test observations**

267 The vertical loads on interior column and each
 268 exterior column were increased simultaneously to
 269 the design test load. There was not any observable

270 damage during the period of vertical load
 271 application. Flexural cracks initiated at the bottom
 272 of the beam in the first floor near the interior
 273 beam-column joint at a drift ratio of 1/600 for
 274 PCF-1 and 1/1200 for PCF-2. The early crack in
 275 PCF-2 is mainly because the concrete sectional area
 276 of the beam in PCF-2 is reduced with the presence
 277 of the PVC tube. The cracks propagated upwards
 278 with the amplitude of the displacement load. A
 279 through crack was observed in the first floor slab
 280 adjacent to the south interior column at a drift ratio
 281 of 1/200 for both specimens. Spalling of concrete
 282 was first seen at the beam end in the second floor at
 283 a drift ratio of 1/28 for PCF-1 and 1/50 for PCF-2.
 284 The longitudinal tensile reinforcement of the beam
 285 buckled afterward. The concrete at the column base
 286 began to spall at a drift ratio of 1/25 for both
 287 specimens. The concrete damage in the final state
 288 was shown in Fig 8. The region of spalling in
 289 PCF-1 was larger than that in PCF-2, which
 290 indicated that the damage was more serious in
 291 PCF-1.

Hysteresis Curves

292 The load-displacement ($P-\Delta$) hysteresis curves are
 293 shown in Fig 9. The maximum lateral capacity of
 294 PCF-1 was 273.5kN at a positive displacement of
 295 57.7mm and -258.0kN at a negative displacement
 296 of -63.1 mm, respectively. The maximum lateral
 297 capacity of PCF-2 was 290.5kN at a positive
 298 displacement of 60.8 mm and -267.5kN at the a
 299 negative displacement of -61.1 mm, respectively.
 300 Both specimens exhibited post peak softening due
 301 to crushing of concrete and buckling of rebar in
 302 compression.
 303 The envelope curves of the two specimens are
 304 shown in Fig 10. The curves are obtained by
 305 connecting the peak points of the first cycles at each
 306 level of displacement amplitude. The yield point,
 307 ultimate point and collapse point can be determined
 308 according to the method proposed by Tang[35].
 309 These performance parameters are given in Table 3.
 310 Specimen PCF-2 (with debonded reinforcement)
 311 has an 8% increase in displacement ductility than
 312 the bonded specimen PCF-1.

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(a) Elevation

(b) Plan

Fig 7 Test setup

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(a) Beam (PCF-1)

(b) Column (PCF-1)

(c) Beam (PCF-2)

(b) Column (PCF-2)

Fig 8 Concrete damage

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(a) PCF-1

(b) PCF-2

Fig 9 Load-displacement ($P-\Delta$) curves

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322 **Secant stiffness**

323 Secant stiffness is defined as the slope between the
324 peak point of a certain cycle and the zero point
325 which can be expressed as follow

$$326 \quad K_i = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 P_j^i}{n\Delta_j} \quad (1)$$

327 Where K_i is secant stiffness, Δ_j is the displacement
328 amplitude at the j^{th} level. P_j^i is the peak load of the
329 i^{th} cycle at a displacement amplitude of Δ_j .
330 The secant stiffness of the specimens decrease

331 approximately at an exponential rate with the drift
332 ratio because of cumulative damage as shown in
333 Fig 11(a). The secant stiffness of PCF-1 and PCF-2
334 are compared in Fig 11(b), in which R_K is the ratio
335 of secant stiffness of PCF-2 to that of PCF-1. The
336 initial lateral stiffness was slightly smaller in the
337 debonded specimen PCF-2 than the traditional
338 specimen PCF-1 because of the decreased strain in
339 the debonded reinforcement. The stiffness of PCF-2
340 was larger than that of PCF-1 when the drift ratio
341 become large. This was due to the larger
342 deterioration of the traditional frame PCF-1.

Fig 10 Envelope curve

Table 3 Performance parameter

Specimen	Direction	Yield		Ultimate		Collapse		Ductility u_{Δ}
		P_y /kN	Δ_y /mm	P_{max} /kN	Δ_{max} /mm	P_u /kN	Δ_u /mm	
PCF1	+	238.0	27.8	273.5	60.7	232.5	98.9	3.5
	-	-236.5	-33.2	-258.0	-60.1	-219.5	-101.0	3.0
PCF2	+	251.0	30.5	281.0	60.8	238.8	104.0	3.4
	-	-240.0	-27.3	-264.5	-60.1	-224.8	-98.9	3.6

(a) Secant stiffness

(b) Stiffness analysis curves

Fig 11 Secant stiffness and analysis curves

Energy dissipation capacity

The energy dissipation capacity is an important index for seismic performance of structures. The cumulative dissipated energy E_{cu} versus top displacement is illustrated in Fig 12(a). For both specimens, the energy dissipation increased with the displacement load. PCF-2 exhibited a higher energy dissipation at lower drift ratios ($\leq 1\%$). At greater drift ratios ($>1\%$), PCF-1 had higher energy dissipation because of the larger region for concrete

damage. In order to further evaluate the energy dissipation capacity, equivalent viscous damping ratios for both specimens are compared. The equivalent viscous damping ratio ζ_{eq} is obtained as follows[36].

$$\zeta_{eq} = \frac{E_d}{2\pi K_l \Delta^2} \quad (2)$$

where E_d is the average energy dissipation of the three cycles of the same displacement load amplitude. K_l is the secant stiffness. Δ is the

368 displacement load amplitude. 374 damping than that of PCF-1 for drift ratios below
 369 The equivalent viscous damping ratios versus drift 375 1% because of the early cracking in PCF-2. The
 370 ratio are illustrated in Fig 12(b). The equivalent 376 damping ratio of PCF-1 exceeded that of PCF-1 at
 371 viscous damping ratio decreased with the drift ratio 377 higher drift ratios (> 1%) due to extensive concrete
 372 at lower drift ratios ($\leq 0.25\%$). Then it increase 378 damage in PCF-1
 373 steadily with the drift ratio. PCF-2 had a large 379 .

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(a) Cumulative energy dissipation

(b) Equivalent viscous damping ratio

381 Fig 12 Energy dissipation capacity

382 **Self-centering capacity**

383 The self-centering capability can be evaluated by 408
 384 the relative self-centering efficiency (RSE) 409
 385 proposed by Sideris et. al [37]. The RSE is an index 410
 386 to quantify the ability of a structure to self-cente 411
 387 under reversed cyclic load, which is defined as 412
 388 follows:

389
$$RSE = 1 - \frac{\Delta_{res}^+ - \Delta_{res}^-}{\Delta_{peak}^+ - \Delta_{peak}^-} \quad (3)$$

390 where Δ_{res}^+ and Δ_{res}^- are residual displacement in the 417
 391 positive and negative direction, respectively. Δ_{peak}^+ 418
 392 and Δ_{peak}^- are positive and negative peak 419
 393 displacement, respectively. These parameters are 420
 394 graphically shown in Fig 13. If RSE equals to 1, the 421
 395 system is perfectly self-centering (elastic with no 422
 396 residual deformation). Whereas RSE equals to 0, 423
 397 the system has no self-centering capacity (rigid 424
 398 plastic system). 425

399 RSE is plotted with drift ratio for the two specimens 426
 400 in Fig 14. RSE decreased with drift ratio for both 427
 401 specimens when drift ratio exceeded 1/400, which 428
 402 indicated that the self-centering capacity reduced 429
 403 with the progressive damage. PCF-2 showed a 430
 404 higher self-centering capacity than that of PCF-1 at 431
 405 larger drift ratio (>1%) because of the lower strain 432
 406 in the debonded rebar.

407 **Rebar Strain**

408 The location of the strain gauges is shown in Fig 15.
 409 The strain of the longitudinal rebar in the beam at
 410 drift ratios of 0.25% and 1% is illustrated in Fig 16.
 411 A number of strain gauges failed when the drift
 412 ratio exceeded 1%. The nominal yield strain of steel
 413 rebar is $2 \times 10^3 \mu\epsilon$. The strain of the top
 414 reinforcement of PCF-1 was very close to that of
 415 PCF-2 for both exterior joints and interior joints at
 416 two drift ratios, which indicated the behavior of the
 bonded top reinforcements was similar for the two
 specimens. While the strain of the bottom rebar of
 PCF-2 was generally smaller than that of PCF-1,
 especially in higher drift ratio, the decrease in strain
 due to the debonded rebar was 7.4% and 8.5% at a
 drift ratio of 0.25% for exterior joint and interior
 joint, respectively. At a higher drift ratio of 1%, the
 decrease in strain resulted from the debonding was
 33.5% and 40.2% for exterior joint and interior
 joint, respectively. The transverse reinforcement in
 the panel zone did not experience yielding during
 the test because the maximum recorded strain of the
 transverse reinforcement was $0.8 \times 10^3 \mu\epsilon$, for both
 specimens, which was lower than the nominal yield
 strain of steel rebar.

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Fig 13 Diagram of self-centering index

Fig 14 Self-centering capacity

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Fig 15 Location of strain gauges

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(a) Exterior joint (0.25% drift ratio)

(b) Interior joint (0.25% drift ratio)

Fig 16 Rebar strain

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440 **Performance assessment**

441 The performance of both specimens is evaluated
442 according to ACI 374 [38] to check if they satisfy
443 the acceptance criteria for new reinforced concrete
444 moment frames designed for regions of high
445 seismic risk. The results are listed in Table 4. K_{ini} is
446 the initial stiffness calculated as the secant stiffness
447 of the first cycle at a displacement of 5 mm. K_{35} is
448 the secant stiffness from a drift ratio of -0.0035 to
449 drift ratio of 0.0035 for the third cycle under the
450 displacement loading of 105 mm (drift ratio
451 =0.035). P_n is the nominal lateral resistance of the
452 test specimen determined using specified geometrical
453 properties, specified compressive strength of
454 concrete and specified yield strength of
455 reinforcement. Besides, two basic conditions
456 namely static equilibrium and compatibility of
457 strains shall be satisfied. Actually, P_n is obtained
458 from the fiber beam-column model using the
459 nominal material strength. The fiber beam-column
460 model is described in the section of numerical
461 modeling of this paper. P_{max} is the maximum lateral

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Table 4 Performance assessment according to ACI 374

Specimen	Direction	Stiffness kN/mm		Resistance kN			P_{max} / P_n	P_{35} / P_{max}	K_{35} / K_{ini}	β_{35}	Remark
		K_{ini}	K_{35}	P_n	P_{max}	P_{35}					
PCF-1	+	20.9	1.15	236.5	273.5	209.1	1.16	0.765	0.055	0.271	Acceptable
	-	-21.0	-1.08		-258.0	-197.0					
PCF-2	+	22.9	1.25	235.4	281	215.5	1.19	0.767	0.055	0.275	Acceptable
	-	-17.3	-1.15		-264.5	-200.4					

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462 resistance of the test specimen. P_{35} is the peak
463 lateral load of the third cycle at a drift ratio of 0.035.
464 β_{35} is the relative energy dissipation ratio for the
465 third cycle at a drift ratio of 0.035.

466 According to ACI 374 [38], the acceptance criteria
467 for performance of the test specimen are
468 summarized as follows:

- 469 1) The peak load at a drift ratio of 0.02 shall be
470 equal to or greater than P_n .
- 471 2) The ratio of P_{max}/P_n shall not exceeds the
472 specified overstrength factor, which is equal to 1.2
473 for the test specimen.
- 474 3) The ratio of P_{35}/P_{max} shall be not less than 0.75.
- 475 4) β_{35} shall be not less than 1/8.
- 476 5) The ratio of K_{35}/K_{ini} shall be equal to or greater
477 than 0.05.

478 Based on the test data and analysis results, the
479 performance of both specimens is satisfied with the
480 acceptance criteria in ACI 374 [38], which indicates
481 that the precast system is applicable to high seismic
482 regions.

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488 **Numerical modeling**
489 To accurately model the nonlinear behavior of
490 precast concrete frames, two-dimensional finite
491 element models were developed using SAP2000
492 [39] as shown in Fig 17. The column and the beam
493 including the floor slab were modeled by the fiber
494 beam-column elements. The debonded rebar was
495 modeled using one-dimensional 300 mm long
496 spring elements. To maintain compatibility and
497 provide the appropriate force equilibrium the spring
498 is connected to the centroid of the fiber beam
499 elements using rigid links. The fiber beam element
500 in the region of the spring element do not include
501 the bottom reinforcement fibers for the debonded
502 specimen PCF-2 (section B-B in Fig 17). The
503 force-displacement relationship of the spring
504 element can be calculated based on the stress-strain
505 curves of the rebar. The adopted modeling scheme
506 has been well established in previous studies
507 [40-43].
508 The uniaxial stress-strain curve of the concrete fiber
509 is shown in Fig 18. Before the peak compression
510 strain ϵ_0 , the stress-strain curve assumes a parabolic
511 relation. When the strain exceeds the peak strain
512 the stress-strain has a linear relationship to a point
513 of $(2\epsilon_0, 0.85\sigma_0)$ [44]. The hysteretic type of
514 concrete is used for modeling the hysteretic
515 behavior of the concrete fiber [45].
516 Fig 19 illustrates the uniaxial stress-strain curves
517 for rebar fibers. In tension strain hardening stage
518 the stress-strain curve has a parabolic form. To
519 account for buckling of rebar in compression as
520 observed in the test, Rajesh and Koichi's model [46]

521 is used as shown in Fig 18b. In their model, an
522 intermediate point (ϵ^*, σ^*) is established, after which
523 a constant softening stiffness of $0.02E_s$ is assumed
524 until the stress equals to $0.2f_y$. The stress-strain
525 relation after yielding is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_i} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{\sigma^*}{\sigma_i}\right) \left(\frac{\epsilon - \epsilon_y}{\epsilon^* - \epsilon_y}\right), \epsilon_y < \epsilon \leq \epsilon^* \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma \geq 0.2f_y; \sigma = \sigma^* - 0.02E_s(\epsilon - \epsilon^*), \epsilon > \epsilon^* \quad (5)$$

526 Where σ_i and σ^* are tensile stresses corresponding
527 to ϵ (current strain) and ϵ^* (strain at intermediate
528 point), respectively.

529 The intermediate point (ϵ^*, σ^*) can be obtained as
530 follow:

$$\frac{\epsilon^*}{\epsilon_y} = 55 - 2.3\sqrt{\frac{f_y}{100} \frac{S}{D_b}}, \text{ and } \frac{\epsilon^*}{\epsilon_y} \geq 7 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\sigma^*}{\sigma_i} = 1.1 - 0.016\sqrt{\frac{f_y}{100} \frac{S}{D_b}}, \text{ and } \sigma^* \geq 0.2f_y \quad (7)$$

531 where S and D_b are spacing of stirrups and diameter
532 of rebar, respectively. Kinematic hysteretic rule is
533 used for the rebar fibers.

534 The plastic hinge length can be determined using an
535 empirically validated formula. Paulay and Priestley
536 [47] proposed that a good estimation of the length
537 of plastic hinge for reinforced concrete members
538 can be obtained from the following:

$$l_p = 0.08L + 0.022f_y D_b \quad (8)$$

539 where L is a cantilever length or the distance
540 between the point of inflection and the point of
541 maximum moment of the member.

Fig 17 Finite element modeling of precast concrete frame

Fig 18 Stress-strain curves for concrete

Fig 19 Stress-strain curves for rebar

552 **Analysis results**

553 Fig 20a illustrates the comparison of numerical
554 load-displacement curves with test curves for
555 specimen PCF-1. Two sets of analysis curves
556 namely Analysis-R and Analysis-T, are presented
557 They are the results from the model with
558 rectangular beam sections and T beam sections

559 respectively. Generally, the shape of the analysis
560 hysteretic curves fits well with that of the test
561 results. The predictions of the rectangular beam
562 model underestimate the load-carrying capacity of
563 the frame. While the results of the T beam model
564 overestimate the capacity. This is because the stress
565 in the floor slab varies with distance from beam

axis. To account for the effect of uneven stress in the floor slab, the concept of effective width is employed for the analysis of T beam section. Fig. 20b shows the analysis results from the models with effective width from 350mm to 950mm. It can be clearly seen that the predictions of the model with an effective width of 750 mm fit best with the test results. This conforms to ACI 318-14 [32] which recommends an effective flange width equal to quarter of the beam span. Therefore, an effective width of 750mm is used in the subsequent analysis of PCF-2.

Numerical load-displacement curves of PCF-2 are compared with the test results as shown in Fig. 21a. The numerical model slightly overestimates the lateral load capacity when the top displacement exceeds 105mm, which corresponds to a drift ratio of 0.035. This can be attributed to the spalling of concrete at the final stage of the test. Nevertheless, the stiffness, the ultimate capacity and the unloading and reloading behavior were predicted with reasonable level of accuracy.

The effect of varying debonded length were examined analytically as illustrated in Fig. 21b. The load carrying capacity decreases slightly with increased debonding. This result is compatible with past test results of concrete cantilever column with partially and fully debonded rebar [25]. The maximum tensile strains of gauge S1 at debonded rebar (see Fig. 15) versus debond length are illustrated in Fig. 22 for drift ratios of 0.25%, 1%

and 2%. The tensile strain in the debonded rebar reduces with the debond length, especially at higher drift ratios. The decrease of rebar strain as debonded length is increased from 300mm to 600mm are 40.5% and 47.8% for drift ratios of 0.25% and 2%, respectively.

Despite its reasonable accuracy, the proposed model has two obvious limitations. One is that the stress-strain relationships of the bonded and unbonded reinforcement considering buckling is determined according to a single S/D_b ratio of 8.33 in Eqs. (4)-(7). However, it is observed from the test that the reinforcement of the debonded specimen buckled at a drift ratio of 0.025, which was earlier than that of the bonded one (a drift ratio of 0.035). Also, it is indicated from Euler's theory that the buckling length of the debonded rebar depends not only on the spacing of the stirrups but also on the boundary conditions, which in this case are the constraint conditions of the PVC tube and the concrete cover. Another limitation is that the proposed model is unable to predict the onset of buckling because this information is not provided in the constitutive relationship of the reinforcement. As there are lack of test evidence on how to determine the buckling behavior of the debonded rebar, especially the buckling length and the onset of buckling, further experimental study on these topics are necessary and will be the work in the future.

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Fig. 20 Load-displacement curves for PCF-1

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Fig 21 Load-displacement curves for PCF-2

Fig 22 Maximum tensile strain of S1

Conclusion

This paper presents experimental and numerical studies of the seismic performance of precast concrete frames with debonded reinforcement at plastic hinge locations. The system consists of precast beams and slabs with cast-in-place columns and a composite topping slab. The findings of this research are as follows:

Specimen PCF-2 (with debonded reinforcement) has an 8% increase in displacement ductility than the bonded specimen PCF-1.

The initial lateral stiffness is slightly smaller in debonded specimen PCF-2 than the traditional specimen PCF-1 because of the decreased strain in the debonded reinforcement. The stiffness of PCF-2 is larger than that of PCF-1 when the drift ratio becomes large. This is due to the large deterioration of the traditional frame PCF-1.

Specimen PCF-2 exhibited a higher energy dissipation capacity at lower drift ratios ($\leq 1\%$). On the contrary, at greater drift ratios ($> 1\%$), PCF-2 had a higher energy dissipation capacity because of the larger region for concrete damage. PCF-2 had larger damping ratio than that of PCF-1 for drift ratios below 1% because of the early cracking in

PCF-2. The damping ratio of PCF-1 exceeded that of PCF-1 at higher drift ratios ($> 1\%$) due to extensive concrete damage in PCF-1.

PCF-2 shows a higher self-centering capacity from 1% to 4% than that of PCF-1 at larger drift ratio ($> 1\%$) because of the lower strain in the debonded rebar.

Debonding of reinforcement at plastic hinge region reduces the strain of the debonded reinforcement. The decrease in strain due to the debonded rebar is 7.4% and 8.5% at a drift ratio of 0.25% for exterior joint and interior joint, respectively. At a higher drift ratio of 1%, the decrease in strain resulted from the debonding is 33.5% and 40.2% for exterior joint and interior joint, respectively.

The performances of both specimens are satisfied with the acceptance criteria in ACI 374 [38], which indicates that this precast system is applicable to high seismic regions.

Based on the numerical analysis, the precast concrete frame with debonded rebar can be accurately simulated through the fiber beam-column model considering the rebar debonding and buckling. The effective flange width could be taken as 750mm, which is a quarter of the

682 beam span. The load carrying capacity decrease
683 slightly with increased debonding. The tensile strain
684 in the debonded rebar reduces with the debond
685 length, especially at higher drift ratios. The
686 decreases of rebar strain from debond length of
687 300mm to 600mm are 40.5% and 47.8% for drift
688 ratios of 0.25% and 2%, respectively.

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